

STUDY OF PAINTING PRETREATMENT OF CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES FOR AUTOMOTIVE APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

For many years, carbon fiber reinforced polymer matrix (CFRP) composite is well recognized for the light property and remarkable performances, and its advanced applications in high-end industries such as aerospace and aeronautics. In recent years, for the major concerns of weight saving and new energy, the utilization of CFRP composite on automotive is treated as a prospective tendency by the majorities of OEMS.

In general, the painting quality standards are often very high for automotive exterior parts due to the strict appearance requirement, and in some top standard cases, A-class surfaces are required. On the other hand, CFRP composite for automobile exterior parts have to face the problem of poor original surface conditions and complex contours. Defects such as resin shrinkage, poor resin and pinhole are common on most CFRP composite parts surface. As a result, pretreatment on the surface of composite parts are crucial prior to painting. In addition, the pretreatment process is always time consuming, the pretreatment of CFRP composite surface prior to painting is therefore the key to improve the painting quality and productivity.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of CFRP composites in civil aircraft has been developed gradually over the past decades, and the related technologies are relatively mature. In recent years, the big potential market of CFRP composite in automotive applications has already caused worldwide attention. However, the related technologies for CFRP composites on automotive parts are still on the preliminary stage due to limited experiences, painted CFRP composite exterior parts are only witnessed in some premium cars and concept prototypes.

In contrary to aviation, automotive industry is much more efficiency sensitive, rapid forming process is favored for the high productivity [1], the chosen material and processing methods of CFRP composite parts are usually determined by the production rate and cost, and these factors will affect

the quality of the original part surface. Here the issue arises: the original surface quality of CFRP composite parts is generally worse than traditional metal or plastic automotive parts, meanwhile the painting requirements of automotive exterior is generally higher than that of aviation parts, therefore the pretreatment of CFRP composite parts becomes essential prior to painting. Above the available experience of painting pretreatment on aviation parts, the automotive exterior parts need to face the concerns of reasonable productivity and higher quality requirements.

This paper will focus on study of the pretreatment methods of CFRP composites prior to painting, in order to meet the quality requirement of automotive exterior parts. Typical CFRP surfaces via the corresponding processing technologies, varies surface pretreatment methods and surface filling (or repairing) materials will be discussed; prospective solutions will be evaluate from the aspect of the ease of operations, materials compatibility and properties, as well as the productivity.

2 SURFACE CONDITIONS

The painting quality of CFRP composite part is very much related to the appearance of the original part surface after demolding. In general, natural surface defects such as pin hole, resin shrinkage and poor resin are commonly seen on CFRP composite part surfaces. The original part surface condition is a combined result of the forming processing materials and methods, including the resin and fiber properties, the processing parameters and the mold's influence. Automotive applications generally require high standard painting quality, for this purpose, short cycle time and low cost should not be the only determinants of the forming process and materials, the part surface should also be considered. A good surface is beneficial to the subsequent painting pretreatment, and the surface quality can be improved by optimizing the forming process and the mold.

2.1 Processing method issue

Different processing methods result in different surface conditions after curing, figures 1 and 2 below compare the typical surface conditions formed by different processing methods.

Figure 1: Vacuum assisted resin infusion processed(VARI)

Figure 2: Prepreg vacuum bag molding processed

Processing method	VARI	Prepreg vacuum bag molding
Materials	3K plain woven fabric + epoxy resin, see figure 1	3K plain woven fabric (prepreg), see figure 2(a)
Curing temperature	80° C	80° C
Curing cycle time	3h	3h

Table 1

The cut panel formed by VARI has an obvious better surface, almost flawless at a glance; whereas the Prepreg vacuum bag molding part has a typical surface with defects of resin shrinkage at the weaving points all over the area, which is mainly caused by the low resin content and low processing pressure at a limited curing time. The poor surface quality will add a lot difficulties to the subsequent painting pretreatment, besides, the tremendous work time added is unacceptable for the mass production of automotive parts.

Despite the premise that correct parameters should be used for any selected processing methods, however, some processes are relatively easier to produce better surfaces. There are other painting pretreatment “friendly” processing methods such as HP-RTM, autoclave and compression molding. With the application of high pressure and temperature, good inner quality and surface quality is generally guaranteed (see figure 3 and 4). However, there is no perfect method: compression molding is limited for complex parts, autoclave is limited for mass production, while HP-RTM satisfies the cycle time, but a high cost is suffered.

Figure 3: HP-RTM processed

Figure 4: Compression molding processed

2.2 Mold issue

Metal mold and GFRP mold are commonly used for CFRP processing. See the figures 5 and 6 below, steel mold generally gives a better part surface quality than GFRP mold. However, selection of the mold material is usually cost driven.

Figure 5: Processed via steel mold

Figure 6: Processed via GFRP mold

Both cut panels are processed by prepreg vacuum bag molding, a typical surface of poor resin is shown in Figure 6, whereas a clear contrast surface is processed via steel mold in Figure 5. The poor resin surface dose not only affect the painting appearance, but also brings potential risks to the painting properties which will be discussed in the subsequent section.

The mold status and the treatment of the mold surface also has great influence on the CFRP part surface. Figure 7 below is a result of uncleaned mold surface before processing (prepreg vacuum bag molding), surface damages were caused during demolding. The existence of dry spots would be most detrimental to painting on CFRP parts.

Figure 7: Dry spots

3 SURFACE PRETREATMENTS

The surface pretreatment is essential to guarantee the painting quality, which is dependent of the substrate material for respective issues. As for traditional automotive parts of steel, electrodeposition technology and phosphating coating are the widespread processes to enable the ability of anti-corrosion, as well as to improve the paint adhesion. Whereas for CFRP parts, the most important issue need to concern is the residues of release agent.

Mold release agent is essential for the processing of CFRP parts, it is generally applied directly to the mold, and the prepared CFRP part is eventually coated with the release agent [2]. Contamination of the release agent residue on the CFRP part surface hinders durable adhesion and painting [3]. Therefore it is a vital to apply the surface pretreatment process to remove the residue release agent.

Sanding is one of the conventional methods that is most widespread, however, the process is very work and cost consuming [4], in most cases, tremendous manual operation is inevitable. However, the surface roughness is increased in the meantime, hence improve the paint adhesion, also surface defects can be spotted and treated during the manual process.

According to the surface treatment process, an overall design of control system about the polish-spray production line of carbon fiber composites based on PLC was established [5]. The utilization of robots for abrading process on automatic line was theoretically achieved, which matches the efficiency for mass production of automotive parts, nevertheless, CFRP parts always have to face varies surface conditions and profile deviations, these issues need to be concerned for feasible industry application.

New surface pretreatment methods, ozone exposure and YAG laser irradiation techniques are investigated to remove contaminates on CFRP parts surfaces, including release agents [6]. However, for epoxy/CF composite, poor adhesion is shown under moderate conditions of ozone exposure and YAG laser radiation, the surface roughness is only slightly increased and there is insufficient removal of release agent. Nevertheless, these technique are expected to be applied widely for other CFRP matrix such as PPS in advanced automatization for automotive applications by optimization of treatment conditions [4].

4 FILLING MATERIALS VIA APPLYING TECHNIQUES

As mentioned above, surface defects are common in CFRP parts, filling materials are often applied to repair the surfaces to improve the appearance, especially for automotive exteriors, intensive work is required in this process due to the high standard quality requirement. The choice of the surface filling material and the applied technique is decided both by the painting requirements and the surface conditions after demolding.

In general, better the surface condition, less work and time is consumed during this process, nevertheless, it is worth noting that even for good surface processing methods which give almost flawless surfaces at a glance, surface defects of pinholes may still exist and become obvious after primer, flash painting under intense light source. See figure 8 below.

Figure 8: pinholes are observed after primer

4.1 Colored painting and transparent coating

Utilization of CFRP is also special for its unique appearance of texture, which would not be seen on any other automotive materials. For this case, lightweight is not the only superiority of using CFRP, but also for the visual effects in exteriors. Generally, application of varnish only would give a transparent coating view that exposes the texture pattern of carbon fibers. For this reason, color of the filling material would be important as it should not affect the look of texture. Anyway, this issue does not exist for colored painting surfaces.

4.2 Surface filling materials

4.2.1 Hole filler

Hole filler can fill tiny surface defects such as pinholes after primer, see figure 9 below, it is single component, can be easily operated and sanded. However, it is only used in small local areas, otherwise, application on large area will cause potential adhesion problems. This filling material is used solely only for good part surfaces, otherwise there should be a combination of using hole filler (on primer) and other filling materials which can be used on a relatively larger area (on substrate).

Process of applying hole filler:

- 1) Searching pinholes under intense light source;
- 2) 400# sanding on the pinhole area;

- 3) Directly apply hole filler to the pinhole;
- 4) 5-10min to dry;
- 5) 600# sanding on the whole primer area.

Figure 9: Pinholes are filled by hole filler (pink spots)

4.2.2 Putty

Putty is generally unsaturated polyester resin based together with curing agent, which is widely used on automotive exteriors for repairing issues: pits, pinholes, shrinkages and cracks can be filled to give a flat surface and smooth finished painting appearance. This material can be used on large area, but only for a limited filling thickness, less than 0.1mm is suggested by experience. It is easily applied and cures fast at room temperature. Advanced putty with small shrinkage is required on CFRP parts for a better stability of the painting properties, however, the long term performance is still a considerable issue.

Selection of putty is possible for both colored and transparent paintings. For transparent coating applications, colorless and black putty can be used. Colorless putty can be used for a lot varieties of surface defects, whereas black putty can be used to fill small defects at/around weaving points, see figure 10 below, the filled defects becomes obscure after varnish is applied.

(a) Appearance after sanding

(b) Appearance after varnish

Figure 10: Surface defects is filled by black putty

Conventional putty is applied manually by a rigid scraper, this process could be time consuming for CFRP part with a bad surface condition due to the repeated work cycle.

Process of applying scraping putty:

- 1) 240# sanding on the CFRP part surface;
- 2) Scraping putty (mixed with curing agent) on the defect areas;
- 3) Usually room temperature drying, may heat in oven in winter if the temperature is too low;
- 4) 240# sanding on the scraped areas;
- 5) Inspect the defect areas, and repeat step 2-4 if necessary.

Spray putty is investigated for surface filling on CFRP parts, it is operated by a spray gun, which is treated a similar way as the primer. This process is more work effective than the treatment of conventional putty, and also enables the possibility of applications on the automatic line for mass production. Nevertheless, sanding is still essential for the adhesion property, yet, no replacement method of automation is available in real industry, which still limits the productivity of CFRP as automotive exteriors. In addition, repeated work cycle may be required, see figure 11 below, some surface defects are still visible after two repeated work cycles, the filling property of spray putty needs to be improved. It is also noted that the scraping putty has a better filling property than the spray putty.

Figure 11: Surface filling by spray transparent putty (sanded surface)

4.2.3 Repairing epoxy resin

Epoxy/CF is most commonly used to form composite part, therefore, the repairing epoxy resin developed for CFRP applications is theoretically compatible with the substrate material, providing a stable long term performance. The two component repairing epoxy resin is suitable for transparent coating applications, which can be used on large area and also for a greater filling thickness, critical surface defects such as dry spots and indentations often occurring at the part corner can be filled. However, there are issues exist in the complicated operations: a) the best storage and operation temperature should be near the room temperature to ensure a good operating viscosity of the mixed resin, as well as for a reasonable pot life; b) The resin should be well mixed (with hardener) and repeatedly scraping on the defect area, make sure defects are filled, flattened and bubble free; c) the cured resin is very hard after curing, a lot work and time would be consumed on sanding. See figure 12 below, the scrapped surface is not flat near the edge, coarse sanding is required in this case.

Figure 12: Surface filling by repairing epoxy resin

Process of applying scraping putty:

- 1) 240# sanding on the CFRP part surface;
- 2) Weigh and mixed the resin and the hardener in the ratio as per instructed;
- 3) Repeatedly scraping the mixed repairing epoxy resin on the defect areas ;
- 4) Room temperature curing (curing time may vary upon on the temperature and humidity);
- 5) Inspect the whole surface after curing, and repeat step 1-4 if necessary.

4.2.4 UV putty

UV putty is also investigated for the transparent coating applications on CFRP in particular, it is a single component material of acrylic resin, which has the advantages of easy operation, fast cure, easy sanding, can be applied on large areas, and also shows a good adhesion property of the CFRP substrate and coatings. Operations of scraping, spraying and hole filling are all possible by changing the viscosity of the resin. The distinctive character of this material is the controllability of curing, unlike other materials which are cured after a certain time of operation, or raise the temperature for a speed up, the curing would be only initiated by the application of specifically designed UV light source. Figure 13 below also shows a good filling property of the UV putty.

(a) Bad surface condition before filling

(b) After surface filling

Figure 13: Surface filling by UV putty

This process can be optimized by combined operations of scraping and spraying together for the best result surface, a smooth surface is shown in figure 14 below.

Figure 14: optimized surface by combined operations

Process of applying UV putty:

- 1) 240# sanding on the CFRP part surface;
- 2) Scraping/Spraying UV putty on the part surface after cleaning;
- 3) Heat at 70° C for 5min to release the volatiles;
- 4) Initiate curing by application of UV for only a few seconds;
- 5) 240#~400# sanding on the CFRP part surface;
- 6) Repeat step 2-5 if necessary;

For relatively better surfaces of smaller and fewer defects, spraying UV putty can be operated by a conventional varnish spraying gun, which means this process is applicable to the automatic line for a raised productivity. However, again, the issue of manual sanding hinders the automation.

4.3 Painting property test

The surface treatment and filling material has great influence of painting properties. Specimen surfaces filled by of conventional putty (black), repairing epoxy and UV putty were produced for tests. Typical painting property tests were taken and shown in table 2 below:

Property test	Standard	Method	Results
Adhesion	GB/T-1720	Cross cut test	Grade 0 adhesion for all specimens
Temperature change test	Enterprise standard	4 test cycle: 40° C, 95%RH, 16h; -40° C, 3h; 85° C, 6h	No color change; no appearance change; grade 0 adhesion for all specimens.
Xenon lamp test	Enterprise standard	Xenon lamp of 0.55Wm, 340nm; Testing time of 1000hr	Color change for all specimens, most affected for epoxy; losing adhesion for conventional putty and epoxy

Table 2

Figure 15: grade 0 adhesion by cross cut test

Figure 16: grade 4 adhesion after Xenon lamp test

Figure 17: grade 5 adhesion after Xenon lamp test

All specimens undergo a color change of yellow due to the substrate material is epoxy based, which is not resistant to UV light aging under the xenon lamp test, therefore, there is no doubt the situation becomes most serious for application of repairing epoxy resin. As mentioned, epoxy as the most important matrix material is extensively used in carbon fiber products, anti-UV aging resistance would be a key issue for the applications of CFRP on automotive exteriors with the appearance of fiber textures. (Note: this is different from UV light initiation on UV putty.)

5 CONCLUSIONS

The advantages of lightweight and high performances of CFRP composite has drew worldwide OEMs' attention, for recent year, processing method and materials were investigated and optimized for mass production of automotive industry, e.g. HP-RTM process and fast cure resin. However, as for automotive exterior parts, the painting pretreatment would be the bottleneck which restricts the productivity. Although a good surface of CFRP part is favored for easier surface treatment and the applications of some surface filling material on automatic line is possible, however, manual work is still inevitable for now. In future work, method of efficient release agent removal on automatic line still needs to be optimized. In addition, Surface-RTM in combined operation with HP-RTM line is another perspective solution for mass production which may avoid the painting pretreatment issue. Moreover, for exteriors with the exposure of carbon fiber texture for visual effect, the potential issue of UV light aging resistance need to be concerned.

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